

EVOLVE2CARE

*Engaging the Value Of Living Labs to Innovate Care
And Regulatory Environments*

What is it about?

Funded under the EU's **Horizon Europe** Research and Innovation programme, **EVOLVE2CARE is a 2-year project** focusing on **HealthTech experimentation**

The focus

EVOLVE2CARE examines **key barriers and drivers of innovation in HealthTech** with a particular focus on **the Transitional Care sector**.

The use cases

The project scope includes **three** use cases:

- 1. Hospital Discharge Management**
- 2. Remote Monitoring and Home-Based Care**
- 3. Inclusive Technologies for Aging and Chronic Care**

The matchmaking

The project will run a **campaign for innovators across Europe** to bring them into collaboration with **Health and Wellbeing Living Labs**, certified by the European Network of Living Labs.

Discover more about EVOLVE2CARE

Evolve2Care

EVOLVE2CARE HorizonEU

Funded by
the European Union

The EVOLVE2CARE partnership

ΑΡΙΣΤΟΤΕΛΕΙΟ
ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Project coordination
Greece

European
Network of
Living Labs

European Network of Living Labs

Association of Living Labs
Belgium

Anthology Ventures JSC

Business acceleration
Bulgaria

SPLOROTECH SL

Innovation matchmaking
Spain

ViLabs (CY) LTD

Outreach and Exploitation
Cyprus

Open Call powered by the Accelup platform!

Are you a researcher, or an entrepreneur?! Do you work at R&D for HealthTech?! **Let's connect!**

EVOLVE2CARE will open up an network of Living Labs to innovators **to experiment and validate research outcomes** for the Transitional Care sector! The hosting Living Labs will be recruited through **the Accelup Platform, an online space for wider, simplified, and more efficient** access to the best Living Lab infrastructures and **their research on demand services.**

SCAN HERE TO LEARN MORE
ABOUT THE CAMPAING >>>

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